

Jews and Jewish-Sympathizers in South Arabia

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Entry tags: Arabian Religions, Judeans and Israelites, Jewish Traditions, Abrahamic, Religious Group

Between 275 and 300, the South Arabian kingdom of Ḥimyar managed to subjugate the nearby kingdoms of Saba' and Ḥaḍramawt, and unified the southern part of the Arabian Peninsula. The language of the ancient and renowned kingdom of Saba' was chosen as the official language of the kingdom. All inscriptions dated after the fourth century are classified as Ḥimyarite. In order to further culturally unify their subjects, the king of Ḥimyar Malkīkarib Yuha'min (reigned from about 375 to 400) converted to monotheism around 380. According to the fifth-century Ecclesiastical History by Philostorgius (d. ca. 439), a Christian religious mission of Theophilus the Indian (d. 364) took place in South Arabia after the kingdom's unification. However, we do not possess any source other than Philostorgius claiming that "Theophilus persuaded the king to become Christian" in the fourth century. Two religious communities are in South Arabia during the fourth and fifth centuries. The local Jews influenced the ruling elites, which adopted a cautious form of monotheism which could be defined as "Jewish sympathizing". In some respects, the god invoked by the South Arabian kings and princes resembles the 'High God' venerated in the Graeco-Roman world and in buffer-state regions such as the already mentioned Palmyra. Ḥimyar's becoming monotheistic was a more gradual process than previously thought, a conclusion supported by the religious vocabulary employed in the monumental epigraphic corpus. The Ḥimyarite monotheistic inscriptions of the time contain three different titles to indicate a supreme monotheistic deity. The most common ones are: 'In ("God," also spelled 'Ihn, 'lh, or 'lhn), B'l/Mr' SImyn ("Lord of the Heaven," sometimes "of Earth" is added), and Rhm nn ("Merciful"). Although these theonyms possess blurred connotations, around ten Ḥimyarite inscriptions point to the presence of Jews in late antique South Arabia. Some inscriptions mention "the People of Israel" (s2'bn Ys3r'l), the Jews (Hd/Hwd/Yhd) or the formula "Owner of the Sky God of Israel" (B'(l) SImyn 'lh Ys3r[l]). We also possess an edict granting the construction of a Jewish cemetery. There are many Hebrew and Aramiac loanwords in these Ḥimyarite inscriptions. In addition to two Hebrew inscriptions have been found in South Arabia, a group of epitaphs found outside South Arabia can be also attributed to Jewish Himyarite emigrants. The Ḥimyarite kings' choice to adopt a monotheism inspired by Judaism potentially had political implications, distancing Ḥimyar from Rome, Aksūm, and the surrounding federations of Arabia.

Date Range: 275 CE - 530 CE

Region: South Arabia

Region tags: West Asia

Ḥimyar (4-6th centuries CE)

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Grasso, Valentina A. "A Late Antique Kingdom's Conversion: Jews and Sympathizers in South

Arabia." *Journal of Late Antiquity* 13, no. 2 (2020): 352-382.

–Source 2: Robin, Christian Julien. *Le judaïsme de l'Arabie antique: actes du Colloque de Jérusalem* (Février 2006). Turnhout: Brepols.

–Source 3: Gajda, Iwona. 2017. "Remarks on Monotheism in Ancient South Arabia." In *Islam and Its Past: Jahiliyya, Late Antiquity, and the Qur'an*, edited by Carl Bakhos and Michael Cook, 247–56. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

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Reference: . Naveh, Joseph. 2003. "A Bilingual Burial Inscription from Saba." *L'Étonné* 5763: 117-20..

Reference: . – Bowersock, Glen W. , *The Crucible of Islam.* Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2017..

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://dasi.cnr.it/>

– Source 1 URL: https://referenceworks.brillonline.com/entries/encyclopaedia-of-islam-1/himyar-SIM_2811?s.num=9

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: See online sources.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Between 275 and 300, the South Arabian kingdom of Ḥimyar managed to subjugate the nearby kingdoms of Saba' and Ḥaḍramawt, and unified the southern part of the Arabian Peninsula. The language of the ancient and renowned kingdom of Saba' was chosen as the official language of the kingdom. In order to further culturally unify their subjects, the king of Ḥimyar Malkīkarib Yuha'min (reigned from about 375 to 400) converted to monotheism around 380. Two religious communities are in South Arabia during the fourth and fifth centuries. The local Jews influenced the ruling elites, which adopted a cautious form of monotheism which could be defined as "Jewish sympathizing". Jews, Jewish-Sympathizers in South Arabia, Christians (both Miaphysite and Dyophysite) are attested. It is plausible that pagan communities are present (esp. in the third and fourth centuries). Zoroastrians may have reached the region at the end of the sixth century.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: A clear example is the massacre of the Christians of the oasis of Najrān around 523 by the Jewish ruler of Himyar.

Specific to this answer:

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Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The theonyms attested in the royal inscriptions between fourth and fifth centuries possess blurred connotations, hinting at a "accommodating" and gradual shift from paganism to monotheism. The most common theonymns are: 'In ("God," also spelled 'lhn, 'lh, or 'lhn), B'I/Mr' SImyn ("Lord of the Heaven," sometimes "of Earth" is added), and Rhḡ nn ("Merciful").

Although these theonyms possess blurred connotations, around ten Ḥimyarite inscriptions point to the presence of Jews in late antique South Arabia. Some inscriptions mention “the People of Israel” (s2’bn Ys3r’l), the Jews (Hd/Hwd/Yhd) or the formula “Owner of the Sky God of Israel” (B’(l) S1myn ’lh Ys3r[’l]). We also possess an edict granting the construction of a Jewish cemetery. There are many Hebrew and Aramiac loanwords in these Ḥimyarite inscriptions. In addition to two Hebrew inscriptions have been found in South Arabia, a group of epitaphs found outside South Arabia can be also attributed to Jewish Himryarite emigrants.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: As previously mentioned, a clear example is the massacre of the Christians of the oasis of Najrān around 523 by the Jewish ruler of Himyar.

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Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: Broadly speaking, the Jews did, but we are uncertain about the communities of late antique South Arabia.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: For the Jews.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: For the sympathizers.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Literary sources suggest that the last Jewish ruler of South Arabia attempted to convert Christians to Judaism between 522 and 525.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The Jews sympathizers belonged to the elites of South Arabia. They were often rulers.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Literary sources suggest so under the last Jewish ruler of South Arabia (522-525).

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Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is an impossible question to answer in a span of three centuries.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Jews and Jewish-Sympathizers were the main religious groups of 4-5th centuries Himyar.

We do not have any monumental polytheistic inscription for this period, and we possess very sporadic Christian material (from the end of the fifth century onwards).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are no traces of South Arabian Scriptural materials. There are only a few mentions in literary accounts produced outside the Arabian Peninsula. No pre-Islamic Arabian Bible survives.

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Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Temples, churches, and synagogues have been found in South Arabia. For an example of a South Arabian synagogue see Tobi, Yosef. “The Jews of Yemen in Light of the Excavation of the Jewish Synagogue in Qanī (Poster).” *Proceedings of the Seminar for Arabian Studies* 43 (2013): 349–56. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/43782890>.

Specific to this answer:

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Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: We possess an edict granting the construction of a Jewish cemetery (l-qtbr b-hn 'yhdn), four plots “to bury the Jews ('yhdn), with the assurance (hymntm, an Aramaism) that they not be buried with non-Jews (interestingly indicated as 'rmym) to fulfil the obligations towards the Jews. The edict is written by the qayl (leader) of the Mdḥ y m tribe, and further grants the construction of a religious building.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: We do not know if they were still in use in the third centuries. It is unlikely considering

the rulers' official conversion to monotheism.

Altars:

– Field doesn't know

Devotional markers:

– Yes

Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– No

Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: One seal belonging to the definitively Jewish corpus of South Arabia depicts a menorah. See Robin, Christian. J. 2004. "Himyar et Israël." *Comptes rendus des séances de l'Académie des Inscriptions et Belles-Lettres* 2: 831-908.

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Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Some public spaces

Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Field doesn't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear if the Jews of South Arabia believed in an afterlife. In some classical Jewish materials there are teachings on life after death, so it may be possible that the Himyarite Jews shared this belief. As the Jewish South Arabian community is not mentioned in any rabbinic source from outside Arabia, new sources are needed for a definitive answer on the matter.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

A supreme high god is present:

– I don't know

Notes: The terminology employed in this corpus is vague and bears resemblance to terminology employed in other late antique contexts, where the veneration of a “High God” and cautious sympathies towards monotheism offered a solution to the rulers’ desire to reshape identities and cults in a wider, syncretistic social framework.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: The only non-human supernatural being is the High God of Himyar. No inscription indicates any form of belief in supernatural creatures such as angels and demons (e.g., the Islamic jinn). Accordingly, we cannot answer any questions about their relationship with humans and how humans perceived them.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Prayers often thank the High God.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

– Yes

Notes: The Ḥimyarite monotheistic inscriptions of the time contain three different titles to indicate a supreme monotheistic deity. The most common ones are: 'In ("God," also spelled 'lhn, 'lh, or 'lhn), B'l/Mr' SImyn ("Lord of the Heaven," sometimes "of Earth" is added), and Rhm nn ("Merciful"). There are no other supernatural beings.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The Ḥimyarite monotheistic inscriptions of the time contain three different titles to indicate a supreme monotheistic deity. The most common ones are: 'In ("God," also spelled 'lhn, 'lh, or 'lhn), B'l/Mr' SImyn ("Lord of the Heaven," sometimes "of Earth" is added), and Rhm nn ("Merciful").

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: B'l/Mr' SImyn ("Lord of the Heaven," sometimes "of Earth" is added).

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Merciful.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do

(future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– No

Notes: The Jews unlikely did so, but it is possible that the Jews-sympathizers did, at least in the primordial phase of monotheism.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

Notes: There is only one supreme god. For supernatural beings in pre-Islamic Arabia see Valentina A. Grasso (Forthcoming, Spring 2023). "Historicizing Ontologies: Qur'ānic Supernatural Creatures between Ancient Topoi and Emerging Traditions", *Journal of Late Antiquity* (Spring 2023).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: The High God mostly answers prayers. Many pre-Islamic Arabian inscriptions located in the north and in the south of the peninsula include an invocation to the god to curse the writers' enemy. If the inscriptions are epitaphs, the writer invites god to curse who profanes the tomb. God is also often able to support the completion and construction of buildings (see inscription DhM 287).

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Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - No
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - No
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - No
 - ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
 - ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious

group:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - No

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - No

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Field doesn't know

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Field doesn't know

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: Mentions of the Messiah appear in the following Christian period of South Arabia. No South Arabian inscription dated to the pre-Christian period bears this information.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is an eschatology present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As mentioned above, no South Arabian inscription dated to the pre-Christian period bears this information.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We can assume that most of the Jewish norms of the time also applied to this community but we do not have enough indigenous data to answer this question with certainty.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no mention in the inscriptions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no mention in the inscriptions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no mention in the inscriptions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no mention in the inscriptions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no mention in the inscriptions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: Circumcision was plausibly required. According to Philostorgius, there were polytheists in South Arabia who practiced circumcision, influenced by a Jewish community (Philost. 3.4).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no mention in the inscriptions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no mention in the inscriptions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no mention in the inscriptions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no mention in the inscriptions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no mention in the inscriptions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no mention in the inscriptions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no mention in the inscriptions but it is plausible.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Tattoos/scarification:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Circumcision:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Food taboos:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: As suggested by an alabaster sculpture today at the MET.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Dress:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Ornaments:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: Aramaic words are often used.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Kingdom. The conquest of Central Arabia lasted a few years. During that period, we could define the polity as "empire".

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: The inscription mentions repairs to the Marib dam.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: The Jewish-Sympathizer rulers surely had an army.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The army of the Jewish ruler of South Arabia between 523-5 fought against the army of the Aksumite king.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: This is proven by the lack of external aids during the Aksumite invasion of the sixth century.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 275 CE - 575 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: We possess over 15,000 inscriptions coming from this area which date from the late second millennium bce to the sixth century ce. These inscriptions employ one script, known as Sabean (so called because it was invented in the kingdom of Saba'). The Jewish-Sympathizers use Sabean, but the Jews write in Hebrew/Aramaic. At Sū 'ar (modern Jordan), a bilingual Palestinian inscription written in Aramaic and Ḥimyarite has been found. This inscription testifies that the South Arabian Jews who emigrated to Palestine called their god Rhḥnn. Furthermore, the inscription shows many Aramaisms, which are attested in the wider monotheistic corpus of South Arabia. See Naveh, Joseph. 2003. "A Bilingual Burial Inscription from Saba.", *L'Ésonénu* 5763: 117-20.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: They use the Himyarite calendar.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

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